

been avoided, probably, because it occurs at high altitudes in difficult terrains. In Kashmir the plant species grows above 3,800 m altitude in the fields of Apharwat, Tous maidan, Konsarnag, Amarnath and Harmukh mountains. For the present study the plant material was procured from Harmukh (3,900 m) mountain through the help of local Gujars.

S. sacra is a herbaceous perennial, densely wooly, stem 15–20 cm long, hollow unbranched, covered by a rosette of leaves at the base, leaf sessile, pinnatifid, 5–8 cm long, black, smooth. Involucral heads exposed, globose, wooly upto 10 cm diameter, pinkish, achenes 2–3 mm, cylindrical, terrate, pappus plumose and hairy white. Distribution Kashmir (Sapru 489) & Sikkim.

Experimental

For alkaloid determination nearly 10 g dry matter of the plant (flowers and stem), was extracted with ethylacetate and later with CHCl_3 . The extract was made alkaline with NH_4OH (pH 9.0) and then neutralised with 2% H_2SO_4 , made alkaline and extracted with CHCl_3 , and dried overnight over anhydrous MgSO_4 . The concentrated solution was subjected to chromatography over silicagel. The elution was carried with C_6H_6 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{-CHCl}_3$ (4 : 1), CHCl_3 and MeOH, and the solvent was recovered under vacuum. TLC on silicagel (0.1 mm thickness) coated plates was used for the determination of the purity of various components. The alkaloids were identified according to the recommended physical and chemical procedures as outlined by Gilmann⁴ & others³, and R_f value of each component was confirmed by comparison with the authentic sample.

Terpenoids were isolated from the mother liquor after isolating the alkaloids, with petroleum ether and the extract was checked for the neutral behaviour. The solvent was recovered in vacuum and the extract was subjected to chromatography over Al_2O_3 and Kieselguhr⁵ (4 : 1) in a solution of petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°) at a temperature of 12°–20°. The chromatogram, was eluted with petroleum ether, C_6H_6 , EtOAc, EtOH+ CHCl_3 (1 : 4) successively. On removing the solvents in vacuum, each fraction was subjected to TLC on silicagel and starch (19 : 1)⁷ to determine the homogeneity of the components. R_f values were compared with the authentic samples and confirmation of the components was done according to the methods as outlined by Guenther⁶. TLC spots were analysed under U.V. light.

Results

The alkaloid part gave two main fractions (i) Saussurol (7.0% by wt), m.p. 222°–224°, and (ii) Colchicine (2.0% by weight), m.p. 140°, $\alpha_D^{20} +116^\circ$, δ' (C = 1 : 20 in CHCl_3) and (iii) $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ (0.6%) having $\alpha_D^{20} +108^\circ, 45'$, m.p. 125.7°–126.0°. TLC showed the presence of three more components with R_f values 0.45, 0.67 and 0.74. These components remain unidentified.

The terpenoids present within the aerial parts of the plant are l-cadinol (40.0%), limonene (3.0%), β -amyrenol (0.3%) and its acetate (0.6%). The percentage composition is based on the weight percent.

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Potentiometric Investigations of Monobromo-Acetate and Monoiodoacetate Complexes of Cadmium (II)

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THIS communication reports the investigations of monobromo-acetate and mono-iodo-acetate complexes of cadmium (II) by potentiometric method.

Experimental

Cadmium metal electrodes were prepared by the procedure suggested by Meites and Thomas¹ as in case of our investigations of Copper-Halo-carboxylate complexes². The potentiometric measurements were carried out by procedure similar to that adopted by Ferrel³. S.C.E. was employed as reference.

All the investigations were carried out at constant temperature 30°. Sodium salt solutions of the ligands were used. pH was maintained constant by keeping free acid salt ratio 1 : 20. The ligand concentration in the series of solutions of a system was kept significantly lower than the ionic strength which was adjusted by adding Potassium nitrate.

Results and Discussions

The composition and the overall formation constants " β_j " of the complexes were determined by Leden's⁴ method from the potentiometric data.

The calculated values of the overall formation constants are given in the following table.

Ligand	μ	TABLE		
		[L] Range	β_1	β_2
M.B.A.	0.75	0–0.5M	7.4	6.4
M.I.A.	0.75	0–0.5M	9.7	4.7

Formation of two complexes $[\text{CdX}]^+$ and $[\text{CdX}_2]^0$ (where X represents M.B.A. and M.I.A.) by monobromoacetic and monoiodo acetic acids at ionic strength 0.75 and ligand concentration 0–0.5M is indicated.

Acetic acid is known to form four complexes with Cd(II).⁵ Formation of lesser number of complexes in case of halo-carboxylate ligands investigated may be attributed to their poor complex forming capacity. As Cd(II) is supposed to coordinate with four water molecules in aqueous solutions, the positions remaining short of those occupied by ligands may be supposed to be taken up by water molecules.

Filipovic⁵ *et al* have reported β_1 value (first step formation constant) of Cd-Acetate system as 20 from polarographic measurements. Thus the order of β_1 values of Cd II complexes of monobromo acetic, monoiodo acetic and acetic acid (A) is

The pK values^{6,7} of monobromo acetic, monoiodo-acetic and acetic acids which are 2.92, 3.19 and 4.76 respectively justify the above order of stabilities of complexes of these ligands.

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Gravimetric Determination of Mercury (II) with the ligand 1-imino-3-thioisindoline

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A NEW method for the gravimetric determination of Hg(II) using the sodium salt soln. of the above ligand¹ has been investigated. The above ligand has been used recently for the gravimetric determination of a number of metals by the authors²⁻⁴. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with Hg²⁺ ions at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10 giving an orange red precipitate of mercury complex which is insoluble in most of the organic solvents. The element analysis of the complex shows that the mole ratio of the ligand to metal is 2 : 1.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade and the ligand was prepared by the method of Bagulev and Elvidge.

Element Analysis—Ligand	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solutions were prepared.

- (1) 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline.....about 0.5% sodium salt soln. of the ligand of pH 7.5 to 10.
- (2) Mercuric Chloride.....Exact 1% soln. in water containing very small amount of HCl.

Determination of Mercury (II):

A known volume of 1 to 25 ml of soln. No. 2 was taken and diluted, to it a freshly filtered soln. No. 1 was added in excess (five to six times). An orange red precipitate of mercury complex was obtained, the precipitate was filtered after ten minutes through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed with water several times and dried in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as Hg(C₈H₅N₂S)₂.

The gravimetric factor for Hg(II) is 0.3836.

Element Analysis—Hg(II)

Complex	%C	%H	%N
Found	36.4	1.8	10.8
Required	36.7	1.9	10.7

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY (II) WITH THE LIGAND

Sl. No.	mg metal taken	mg metal recovered	% error
1	5	5.05	1.00
2	5	5.00	—
3	5	5.03	0.60
4	10	10.04	0.40
5	10	10.05	0.50
6	10	10.05	0.50
7	25	25.10	0.40
8	25	25.15	0.60
9	25	25.15	0.60

Interferences :

Most of the common anions do not interfere. Only few cations interfere these includes Cu(II), Ag(I), Cd(II), Au(III), Pb(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Tl(I).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in Table 1, indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for mercury(II) in macro and semi-macro quantities. It is easy to filter the precipitate and bring the precipitate to constant weight within a period of half an hour.

The precision was fair, and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.

The concentration and temperature has no effect on precipitation. At pH < 6 a small amount of the water soluble form of the reagent may be precipitated and at pH > 10 a partial decomposition of the ligand is likely to take place.

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